

Relative viscosity and surface tension of subsoil brines : A case study of Chandan subsoil brine

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Relative viscosity and surface tension of subsoil brines (underground brines) in the temperature range 30–70° have been evaluated wherein the solar evaporation of these brines takes place for obtaining salt and other byproducts.

The solar evaporation of sea water or underground brines is carried out for obtaining salt and other byproducts. Out of 14 million tons of salt currently produced in India, approximately 30% of it is produced by employing the underground brines. The rate of evaporation of these brines not only depends upon the amount of dissolved salts and their nature, but also upon external factors like wind velocity, temperature, relative humidity, etc. The rate of evaporation also depends upon the properties like density, viscosity and surface tension of these brines.

A look at the search of literature informs that only a few data are available for the individual salts^{1,2} and some selected underground brines like sodium-potassium sulfates and sodium-potassium carbonates². But in case of multi-ion equilibrium containing sulfates and chlorides of calcium, sodium, potassium and magnesium, the available literature is limited. So it was decided to study the effect of ionic strength and the temperature on the relative viscosity and surface tension of these underground brines and as a case study, the Chandan Salt underground brines were considered, which lies around 15 km towards North direction from Bhavnagar, Gujarat, having a depth of 400 ft with an initial density of 1.056 (7.6°Be'). Experiments have been conducted to get the data of viscosity and surface tension of these brines at various degree baumé in the temperature range 30–70°.

Results and Discussion

Relative viscosity : In the case of relative viscosity which is an intrinsic property depends mainly on the nature of the dissolved ions and their quantity. A correlation between the relative viscosity and the ionic strength of the brine has been made,

$$\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right) = A\sqrt{I}$$

where, η and η_0 are the viscosities of the underground brine and pure water at the same temperature and I is the ionic strength of the medium and the constant A takes into account the ion-solute as well as ion-ion interactions taking place in the system. The data are given in Table 1. The plots of square-root of ionic strength (I) against

$\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right)$ (Fig. 1) reveal a gradual increase in the values but at higher ionic strength a sharp increase is observed. This indicates that the short range forces are more effective at higher ionic strengths than at lower ones. It can also be seen that as the temperature increases the solvation sphere surrounding the ion slowly breaks down showing a decrease in relative viscosity. In the case of these underground brines a combination of these two factors affect the rate of evaporation of water thereby showing a gradual decreasing tendency as the density/degree baumé increases

Table 1. Relative viscosity of the subsoil brine samples of various degree baumé and temperatures

"Bé	Ionic strength	\sqrt{I}	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°	65°	70°
7.2	0.2371	0.4869	0.932	0.821	0.709	0.689	0.678	0.621	0.561	0.506	0.468
10.6	0.2722	0.5212	1.154	0.987	0.827	0.799	0.775	0.682	0.585	0.533	0.490
14.0	0.2789	0.5281	1.215	1.030	0.877	0.864	0.854	0.739	0.618	0.564	0.517
25.0	0.7361	0.8579	1.798	1.596	1.391	1.292	1.190	1.014	0.812	0.740	0.665
30.0	1.3772	1.1736	2.039	1.792	1.532	1.459	1.377	1.139	0.897	0.812	0.708
33.0	1.4567	1.2069	4.206	3.562	2.909	2.744	2.579	2.215	1.825	1.609	1.413
35.0	1.4911	1.2211	6.287	6.044	5.825	4.692	3.581	3.312	3.029	2.756	2.453

Table 2. Surface tension of subsoil brine samples at different temperatures and various degree baumé

$^{\circ}\text{Bé}$	Ionic strength \sqrt{I}		30 $^{\circ}$	35 $^{\circ}$	40 $^{\circ}$	45 $^{\circ}$	50 $^{\circ}$	55 $^{\circ}$	60 $^{\circ}$	65 $^{\circ}$	70 $^{\circ}$
7.2	0.2371	0.4869	73.84	73.29	72.29	71.01	69.90	68.51	67.31	66.38	65.59
10.6	0.2722	0.5212	74.29	72.96	71.89	71.48	71.39	70.61	69.95	69.04	68.51
14.0	0.2789	0.5281	74.38	76.94	79.14	78.96	78.60	77.21	75.74	72.65	69.49
25.0	0.7361	0.8579	78.29	84.16	90.02	89.46	89.96	88.48	87.80	86.48	85.40
30.0	1.3772	1.1736	83.19	88.27	93.10	92.40	91.50	90.47	89.72	88.03	86.41
33.0	1.4567	1.2069	85.29	90.39	95.21	94.37	93.24	92.44	91.27	90.44	89.21
35.0	1.4911	1.2211	88.48	93.45	98.30	96.74	95.36	94.22	93.26	92.61	92.21

at the same temperature. As the temperature increases there is an accountable reduction in viscosity values and so the evaporation rate is faster during summer seasons as is observed in the fields.

Fig. 1. Effect of ionic strength on the relative viscosity of subsoil brine (Chandan) at different temperatures: (—○—) 35 $^{\circ}$, (—×—) 40 $^{\circ}$, (—×—) 45 $^{\circ}$, (—Δ—) 50 $^{\circ}$, (—Δ—) 55 $^{\circ}$, (—●—) 60 $^{\circ}$, (—●—) 65 $^{\circ}$, and (—□—) 70 $^{\circ}$.

Surface tension: The surface tension of the subsoil brines was determined in the range of 30–70 $^{\circ}$ at an interval of 5 $^{\circ}$ (Table 2). The data indicate that there is a gradual decrease in surface tension values as the temperature increases showing that evaporation rate is faster at higher temperatures. On the other hand, the data indicate that the surface tension of these brines increases with increase in density. Kamnisky³ used empirical equations to correlate the surface tension of sea-brine with that of pure water and

the effect of temperature as

$$\gamma = \gamma_w - 0.144 T + 0.0399 (\% \text{ Cl})$$

where, γ and γ_w are the surface tension of sea-brine and that of pure water at the sea temperature (T), respectively, and % Cl is the percentage of chloride ion in the brine. The above equation agreed fairly well with the present results when applied to the underground brines of Chandan Salt Works.

Experimental

Viscosity was measured by employing a viscometer which was calibrated with respect to distilled water using a constant temperature water-bath ($\pm 0.5^{\circ}$) in the range 30–70 $^{\circ}$ at intervals of 5 $^{\circ}$. The relative viscosity was calculated and when two or three continuous measurements agreed fairly well then only these were considered. The deviation of the results was found to be ± 2 –5%. Similarly, surface tension was measured by the standard capillary method.

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